

Public-private partnership (PPP)

What is PPP?

This financing strategy involves a long-term partnership between public and private entities to deliver public assets and services. In the context of cultural landscapes, examples of PPP include concession and sponsorship contracts, trust funds, and 4P (Public-Private-People Partnerships), where civil communities play a role in the design and management processes.

Key benefits

Key enablers

Examples of financing strategy based on PPP strategy available in the **RescueMe Metarepository** include:

- The Sponge City community in Changsha, China
- The flood-proof district in Bilbao, Spain
- The Prespa Ohrid Nature Trust
- The concession contract for the Royal Villa in Monza, Italy, and many others.

Crowdfunding/ Community financing

What is crowdfunding and community financing?

This financing strategy involves soliciting small contributions from a large number of people. Unlike crowdfunding, which typically appeals to a broad audience, community financing targets a specific and limited group, such as a local community or neighboring municipalities.

Key benefits

Key enablers

Examples of financing strategies based on Crowdfunding/Community financing available in the **RescueMe Metarepository** include:

- The "Adopt a Terrace" initiative in the Brenta River Valley, Italy
- The Community Farms Program and Fund in Canada
- Reward-based crowdfunding led by Le Centre des Monuments Nationaux in France

Impact funding

What is impact funding?

Impact funding seeks to generate social and environmental benefits alongside financial returns. This financing strategy is defined by the intentionality and measurability of its impact, such as funds specifically aimed at achieving socio-cultural outcomes.

Key benefits

Key enablers

Examples of financing strategy based on impact funding available in the **RescueMe Metarepository** include:

- Climate bond financing for adaptation initiatives in Paris, France
- Carbon certification scheme for sustainable land management in Kenya
- Arts & Culture Impact Fund by Nesta in the United Kingdom

Risk management

What is risk management?

This financing strategy is centered on identifying, assessing, and mitigating potential threats to cultural heritage and landscapes, involving the transfer of risks between multiple parties.

Key benefits

Key enablers

An example of financing strategy based on risk management available in the **RescueMe Metarepository** include the case of the Adjusted Gross Revenue insurance for Villa Adriana and Villa D'Este in Italy.

Economic policy instruments

What are economic policy instruments?

This financing strategy includes both incentives, such as subsidies, and disincentives, like taxes, offered by the public or private sector to encourage specific behaviors or support activities aimed at protecting cultural heritage and landscapes.

Key benefits

Key enablers

Examples of financing strategy based on economic policy instruments available in the **RescueMe Metarepository** include:

- Eco-taxes in the Balearic Islands, Spain
- Active subsidies for traditional vineyards in Donana, Spain
- Payment for Environmental Services (PES) schemes in the Coffee Cultural Landscape of Colombia

Grants

What are grants?

This financing strategy is based on non-repayable funds provided by public or private bodies to support specific projects, activities, or objectives, contingent on certain conditions and reporting procedures.

Key benefits

Key enablers

Examples of financing strategy based on grants available in the **Rescuellle Metarepository** include:

- European Economic Area (EEA) grants supporting climate adaptation measures in Bratislava, Slovakia
- Lottery Environment and Heritage Committee in New Zealand

Hybrid funding

What is hybrid funding?

This financing strategy is based on a mix of financial instruments, such as grants, loans (debt), guarantees, equity and quasi equity. It can encompass a range of financial instruments, such as combining loans with EU funds, integrating philanthropic donations with micro-credits and soft loans, utilizing debt swaps and environmental compensations, and incorporating private investments.

Key benefits

Key enablers

Examples of financing strategy based on hybrid funding available in the **RescueMe Metarepository** include:

- Agrosilvopastoral landscape of Puriscal and Turrubares, Costa Rica
- Innovative financing mechanism for preserving traditional housing in Machiya, Japan

Social entrepreneurship

What is social entrepreneurship?

This is a business strategy where organizations or ventures aim to achieve both economic goals and social and environmental objectives. It can take various legal forms, such as foundations, social cooperatives, or associations; business orientations, including for-profit or non-profit; and ownership structures, including public, private, PPP, or ecclesiastical.

Key benefits

Key enablers

Examples of business strategies based on social entrepreneurship available in the **RescueMe Metarepository** include:

- Social enterprise Doh Eain in Myanmar
- Social farms in Sicily, Italy

For further information on the RescueMe project visit the [project website](#)

Income diversification

What is income diversification?

This business strategy involves partially redirecting production resources from the primary activity to new ventures or activities. Examples include diversifying agricultural production by adding processing of agricultural products or small-scale manufacturing, introducing community-based ecotourism, and expanding revenue streams through additional tourism services.

Key benefits

Key enablers

Examples of business strategy based on income diversification available in the **RescueMe Metarepository** include:

- Livelihood diversification for pastoralist women in Tanzania and Kenya
- Community-based eco-tourism in the Northern Cape, South Africa

Climate-smart strategy

What is climate-smart strategy?

This business strategy focuses on climate-smart value creation, aiming to boost agricultural productivity, enhance the resilience of farms and farmers, and contribute to climate change mitigation. It includes the implementation of practices that sequester CO₂ in agricultural landscapes.

Key benefits

Key enablers

Examples of climate-smart business strategy available in the **RescueMe Metarepository** include:

- Winmarleigh carbon farm (UK)
- Biogas initiative in Bali (ID)

Collaborative strategy

What is collaborative strategy?

This business strategy is based on institutionalized cooperation and relies on the active involvement of diverse stakeholders, including government agencies, local communities, non-profit organizations, businesses, and academic institutions. Examples include agricultural cooperatives with a network of farms dedicated to maintaining traditional agri-food systems and community farms that foster collective stewardship of local resources.

Key benefits

Key enablers

Examples of collaborative business strategy available in the **RescueMe Metarepository**:

- Agricultural cooperative in Lanzo Valleys in the Piedmont Region (IT)
- Community farms (CA)

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Territorial branding

What is territorial branding?

This business strategy leverages a set of symbols, cultures, and identities to create distinctive brands, whether through planned or organic development. It focuses on crafting strategies that establish power relations both within and beyond the territory. This approach can enhance the added value of local production and the associated cultural landscape.

Key benefits

Key enablers

Examples of business strategy based on territorial branding available in the **RescueMe Metarepository** include:

- Eco-labelling for the traditional vineyards of Doñana, Spain
- Entrepreneurial strategy based on the promotion of a traditional cultural landscape: the case of Fattoria di Lamole, Italy